

Ageism in the workplace: Challenges and solutions for the inclusion of professionals 45+

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Background

According to the World Health Organisation (WHO) (2021), the concept of ageism refers to stereotypes, prejudices and discrimination against people based on their age and has negative consequences for individuals, institutions and countries (Fragoso & Fonseca, 2022). This phenomenon is present in all spheres of society, such as the social and health sectors, the media, the legal system and companies and organisations. In Europe, one out of three people say they have been victims of ageism (WHO, 2021).

In the labour context, ageism refers to the beliefs and expectations that are placed on workers based on their age, and they can affect people of all ages (Sherman & Hamilton, 1994). It occurs when the organisation's policies, superiors or co-workers have negative attitudes towards a worker based on their age - for example, not providing training to an older worker regarding new digital tools because they think an older person will not be able to learn how to work with a new technology.

Ageism deprives organisations of using the potential of older workers (Posthuma & Guerrero, 2013), decreases job satisfaction and organisational commitment (Kunze et al., 2011), increases absenteeism and conflicts, leading to a reduction in performance and overall productivity (Voss et al., 2018).

Older workers are penalised, for example, in recruitment and selection, integration, assigned duties, career progression, remuneration, selection for training or decisions on transfers, promotions, termination of employment contract or retirement (UNECE, 2019).

In organisations, stereotypes about older workers can be seen in different types of prejudice and beliefs, illustrated in the following fictional quotes:

- *They underperform, have fewer skills and are less motivated and productive.*
- *They are more difficult to train, less flexible and adaptable.*
- *They have less learning capacity and less potential for professional development.*
- *They are more expensive and use more social benefits (Posthuma & Guerrero, 2013).*

PRIORITY45 Project

To meet this challenge and promote the (re)qualification of workers, a consortium consisting of organisations from five European countries – Portugal (coordinator), Spain, Greece, Italy and Slovenia - has been working since December 2022 on the project Promoting employment of 45+

adults through a disruptive training approach - PRIORITY45, co-funded by the Erasmus+ Programme.

The project aims to encourage the upskilling and reskilling of adults over the age of 45, as well as to bring the business sector closer to Adult Education (AE), promoting the importance of establishing training plans for 45+ adults among companies and other organisations, to avoid ageism and discrimination.

To such end, the PRIORITY45 Virtual Course was developed, based on what workers and companies pointed out in the literature and in the project's co-creation activities as the greatest learning needs. Digital literacy, teamwork, innovation or creativity are some of the 22 units in the course, divided into five modules.

Considering the characteristics of the adult learners, the virtual course offers the possibility of choosing their learning path. Participants can complete all 50 hours of the course, choose the modules they want to learn about, or just select the units that interest them the most. The aim is to make learning as flexible as possible, so that it can be better integrated into the adult learner's day-to-day working and personal life.

The variety of approaches presented in the course is also one of its strengths: participants have access to written content, graphics, diagrams and images, short videos, interactive exercises and an assessment component.

This course was designed to be used by individuals who want to develop their skills, but also companies can provide it to improve the skills of their employees.

An effective entente between the business sector and AE brings advantages for workers, but also for companies, specifically increased productivity and competitiveness, which are essential drivers of economic growth (OECD, 2020). In addition, many small and medium-sized enterprises face labour shortages and difficulties in attracting and retaining talent, so targeted training can bridge these gaps by helping to align workers' skills with employers' evolving needs (OECD, 2020). By improving workers' skills, AE also promotes innovation through the introduction of new ideas, technologies and practices, especially in fast-changing sectors or emerging industries, benefiting workers through potential pay rises and career progression (OECD, 2020).

To bring these two areas closer together – industry and AE -, PRIORITY45 has developed a Blueprint to promote strategic co-operation between stakeholders. The Blueprint is divided into five priorities: Promoting lifelong learning; Aligning education with employment needs; Raising awareness of the relevance of AE over 45; Combating ageism; and Strengthening professional and digital skills. For each of the priorities, objectives, results and actions have been defined to target specific groups, such as policy makers, AE providers, adults over 45, among others.

The Blueprint will serve as a practical guide to strengthening the education of adults over 45 years of age, raise awareness in society and involve stakeholders in promoting the inclusion and added value of this age group.

Conclusion

Fighting ageism in the workplace requires a joint effort to raise awareness, training and to change the organisational culture. PRIORITY45 is an innovative initiative, promoting the inclusion and appreciation of 45+ professionals, by offering a digital course focused on the most essential skills

for today's labour market. PRIORITY45's flexible and practical approach respects the needs and experience of workers, enhancing their skills and competences.

By fostering closer ties between the business sector and AE, this project highlights how investment in continuing training not only benefits individuals, promoting career opportunities and increased satisfaction, but also companies, which can capitalise on the potential of a more experienced workforce. The Blueprint, with strategic guidelines for expanding this co-operation, is an important step towards creating more inclusive, innovative and productive working environments.

References

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